

Improving Practice Teachers' Classroom-Based Action Research Capability: The Differential Impact of Project RISE as a Structured Research Capability Pedagogical Intervention

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Abstract

Practice teachers under teacher education programs often face challenges in conducting classroom-based action research, mainly due to limited research training and exposure. This study aimed to examine the effectiveness of Project RISE (Research-Inspired Student Educators), a structured research capability intervention, in improving the self-perceived classroom-based action research skills of practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc. The study used a quantitative quasi-experimental design with a one-group pre-test and post-test strategy. A total of 75 practice teachers were purposefully selected as participants. Their self-reported research capability was measured before and after the two-day seminar-workshop using mean, standard deviation, and a paired t-test. Results showed a significant improvement in the practice teachers' self-perceived ability to conduct classroom-based action research after the intervention. Based on these findings, the study recommends that research capacity-building activities be conducted prior to the deployment of practice teachers. Classroom-based action research training should also be included as a regular part of the teacher education curriculum. Continuous scholarly investigation into education-related challenges, as the Philippine education system continues to face pressing issues that require research-based solutions, must be done. Further studies may expand the design, include other teacher education institutions, and use more objective assessments of research capability.

Keywords: *classroom-based action research, practice teacher, Project RISE, research capability, research capacity building.*

Suggested citation: Abendaño, M.D.O., & Pontillo, A.M.M. (2025). Improving Practice Teachers' Classroom-Based Action Research Capability: The Differential Impact of Project RISE as a Structured Research Capability Pedagogical Intervention. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 3(4), 256-268. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2025.3(4).17

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Introduction

Context and Rationale

Doing research has long been a dreaded requirement among undergraduate students, often leaving many overwhelmed and unprepared. Although it is a crucial part of the curriculum and a non-negotiable component for graduation (Evangelista & Hernandez, 2016), students frequently view research as an uphill battle they are forced to endure (Banu et al., 2022; Mertler, 2024). The guarantee of research to unearth informed solutions to educational problems (Wanasinghe, 2020) is often overshadowed by the reality that many students lack the scientific knowledge and problem-solving skills essential for completing their projects (Mishore & Abate, 2023). Consequently, writing a research paper becomes a burden rather than a learning process as students grapple with its complexity and technical demands (Jilcha, 2025). For many, research is simply the most grueling academic challenge they must face (Clarín et al., 2025; Laradiputra, 2022).

Globally, the issue of conducting research persists, making it not isolated to a single academic community. For instance, college students at Tra Vinh University in Vietnam experienced difficulties with research-related tasks that demanded skills they had yet to master (Ngoc & Ngoc, 2021). A similar problem was reported in Jordan, where undergraduate students faced multiple roadblocks in completing their graduation projects (Altikriti, 2021). Indonesia, on the other hand, showed the same frame of the problem as college students from IAIN Curup expressed frustration and confusion in conducting research, signaling a broader educational flaw in research instruction (Puspita, 2021). These global studies point to a troubling trend that is evident across the globe: students are being pushed into research work with a lack of research skill set, insufficient support, and perhaps unrealistic expectations.

In the Philippines, the situation is equally disheartening. College students from Laoag City have labeled research subjects as terrifying and unavoidable hurdles they must bear to earn their college degrees (Balbag et al., 2024). At the Bataan Peninsula State University, student researchers reported repeated struggles in various research activities, pointing to a systemic gap in research readiness (Magno, 2024). The weight of academic pressure, combined with personal challenges, was also highlighted by students in a private university who found writing research papers both mentally and emotionally exhausting (Campillan, 2019). These local accounts make it clear that there is something fundamentally flawed in how research is taught and approached within the Philippines' higher education institutions.

Locally, in St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc., the problem of conducting classroom-based action research among college students from the education program is becoming more evident and urgent. For the school year 2025–2026, the majority of practice teachers voiced strong concerns about their classroom-based action research, as this type of research was entirely unfamiliar to them. They were unsure of what problems to identify, how to properly structure their papers, and what interventions to implement—an approach completely different from the non-experimental undergraduate theses they were previously trained and familiar with. This shift in research demand left them confused and unprepared. To make matters worse, it has been observed that previous batches of practice teachers were left without a clear

roadmap on how to undertake their action research, resulting in serious difficulties during the actual implementation and delays in fulfilling course requirements.

Despite the centrality of research in higher education, there remains a gap in how college students, particularly future educators, are prepared to undertake it. There is a continuous struggle among undergraduate students as to how to conduct research due to the lack of practical and structured academic writing instruction, which should be an essential component of their coursework (Nenotek et al., 2022). What is more alarming is that research interest among students is on a disturbing decline (Garingan, 2019). Teacher education programs fail to build the confidence needed for sustained inquiry practices among future educators (Aras, 2021), and as a result, they enter the field unprepared for research demands. This highlights the urgent need for teacher education institutions to embed action research in teacher education training programs to better align with the realities of the Department of Education's expectations (Amoto et al., 2024).

The researchers firmly believed that the problem was clear and that immediate action was needed. There is a pressing need to develop and reinforce both global and local efforts to enhance the research competencies of undergraduate students (Adebisi, 2022). Calls for additional studies to unearth the layers of research-related challenges faced by students have been repeatedly stressed, underscoring how much of the problem remains unaddressed (Micabalo et al., 2020). The absence of concrete solutions contributes not only to individual academic failure but also weakens the broader education system and its potential societal contributions (Basu, 2020). Thus, this study aims to fill that gap through Project R.I.S.E. by equipping practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc., with the knowledge and confidence to write, conduct, and report classroom-based action research—an area still largely unexplored in teacher training yet crucial in fulfilling the United Nations' sustainable development goal on quality education.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of Project RISE (Research-Inspired Student Educators) as a structured research capability pedagogical intervention on improving St. Mary's College Baganga Inc., practice teachers' self-perceived classroom-based action research capability. Below are the specific research objectives this study aimed to address:

1. To determine the level of self-perceived classroom-based action research capability among practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc., before the implementation of Project R.I.S.E.
2. To determine the level of self-perceived classroom-based action research capability among practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc., after the implementation of Project R.I.S.E.
3. To examine if there is a significant difference in the self-perceived classroom-based action research capability among practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc., before and after the implementation of Project R.I.S.E.

Null Hypothesis

The null hypothesis established in this study was tested based on an α of 0.05 level of significance.

H_0 1. There is no significant difference in the self-perceived classroom-based action research capability among practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc., before and after the implementation of Project R.I.S.E.

Proposed Innovation, Intervention, or Strategy

Project Research-Inspired Student Educators or R.I.S.E. is a 2-day seminar-workshop designed to strengthen the self-perceived classroom-based action research capability of practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc. This initiative aimed to empower future educators with the knowledge, skills, and confidence to conduct action research in their respective learning environments. Theoretical discussions on the foundations, process, and significance of classroom-based action research in education were all covered on the first day. On the other hand, the application of theoretical learning, where the practice teachers will draft their own classroom-based action research proposals with guided supervision, was done on the second day.

This educational intervention is anchored in Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986), which posits that self-efficacy, which is an individual's belief in their ability to perform a task, is the key to initiating and sustaining learning behaviors. In relation to the proposed intervention, the researchers believed that by providing practice teachers with structured theoretical input and guided proposal writing experiences, Project R.I.S.E. has the potency to strengthen practice teachers' self-perceived capability in conducting classroom-based action research.

Materials and Methods

Action Research Methodology

This study employed a quantitative quasi-experimental design using a one-group pre-test post-test approach to assess the effectiveness of Project R.I.S.E. in enhancing the self-perceived classroom-based action research capability of practice teachers. A total of 83 practice teachers from St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc., initially participated in the intervention. The respondents were selected through purposive sampling based on specific inclusion criteria: male or female, aged 18 and above, currently enrolled as practice teachers, and willing to participate in both the program and the survey. A structured 4-point Likert scale multidimensional questionnaire from the study of Jones et al. (2024) served as the research instrument, with minimal modifications to fit the local context. After data cleaning, 75 responses were deemed valid and qualified for analysis, with eight being excluded due to incomplete or unusable data.

Before the actual data collection, the researcher first secured approval from the school president, who also serves as the college dean, and approval from the program head of the education department. Ethical considerations were upheld by securing informed consent from all respondents. The data-gathering process followed a systematic procedure before and after the Project R.I.S.E. seminar-workshop to measure changes in participants' self-perceived research capability. To analyze the data, the researcher

used mean and standard deviation to answer the descriptive questions of the study. At the same time, a paired t-test was conducted to answer the study's inferential question. The statistical analysis was done using JASP 0.19.3. To be specific, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the level of self-perceived classroom-based action research capability among practice teachers, and a paired t-test was used to answer the question whether there is a significant difference in the self-perceived classroom-based action research capability among practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga, Inc., before and after the implementation of Project R.I.S.E.

Presented in Table 1 is the Gantt chart for the implementation of Project RISE. The pre-implementation phase began in May and continued through the months of June and July. This stage involved planning, coordination with faculty, and preparation of materials for the seminar-workshop. The actual implementation of Project RISE, together with the post-implementation activities such as evaluation and data collection, took place in July. These phases were closely scheduled to ensure that practice teachers received timely support before their deployment.

Meanwhile, Table 2 presents the breakdown of the cost expenditure for the entire project. It includes the budget allocation for materials, resource speakers, meals, venue, printing of modules, and certificates. These expenses were carefully managed to ensure the seminar-workshop was conducted efficiently while staying within budget. As shown in Table 2, the total budget allocated for the implementation of Project RISE amounted to only ₱ 11,820. This amount covered all necessary expenses. The funding was a combination of institutional support and self-funding by the project proponents. Considering that the budget is limited, the project was successfully carried out through careful planning and resource management, proving that meaningful research capacity-building activities can still be implemented even with minimal financial resources.

Table 1. Gantt Chart for the Project RISE Implementation

Phase and Task	Month 1				Month 2				Month 3			
	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4
A. Pre-Implementation Phase												
1. Conduct initial consultation with the education program administrator	■	■										
2. Identify the research problem and target participants			■									
3. Design research framework and methodology				■								
4. Draft and finalize the project proposal					■							
5. Develop seminar-workshop content and activities						■						

Table 2. Cost Estimates for the Project RISE Implementation

Activity	Description/Particular	Quantity	Unit	Unit Cost	Total Amount
A. Pre-Implementation					
Refreshments	Snack	12		₱ 50	₱ 600
Printing of Resource Speaker's Certificate	Printed Certificate	1		₱ 20	₱ 20
B. Implementation Phase					
Resource Speaker's Food (Day 1)	Morning Snack	1		₱ 200	₱ 1,000
	Lunch	1		₱ 300	
	Afternoon Snack	1		₱ 200	
	Dinner	1		₱ 300	
Resource Speaker's Food (Day 2)	Morning Snack	1		₱ 200	₱ 1,000
	Lunch	1		₱ 300	
	Afternoon Snack	1		₱ 200	
	Dinner	1		₱ 300	
C. Post Implementation Phase					
Professional Fee	Resource Speaker's Professional Fee	1		₱ 6,200	₱ 6,200
Publication Fee	Peer-Review Processing Fee	1		₱ 3,000	₱ 3,000
Total	₱ 11,820				
Source of Funding	Combination of institutional and self-funding				

Results

Presented in Table 1 is the result of the descriptive statistics on the self-perceived classroom-based action research capability in terms of mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, social or verbal persuasion, and positive affect as self-reported by practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga Inc., before the implementation of Project R.I.S.E.

Table 3. Level of Self-Perceived Classroom-Based Action Research Capability Among Practice Teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga Inc., Before the Implementation of Project R.I.S.E.

Dimensions	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Mastery Experiences	2.40	0.450	Rarely Manifested
2. Vicarious Experiences	2.57	0.553	Oftentimes Manifested
3. Social or Verbal Persuasion	2.07	0.583	Rarely Manifested
4. Positive Affect	2.33	0.674	Rarely Manifested
Total	2.34	0.388	Slightly Capable

Prior to the implementation of Project R.I.S.E., the St. Mary's College Baganga Inc., practice teachers demonstrated a slight capability in classroom-based action research

($M = 2.34$, $SD = 0.388$). Among the dimensions, vicarious experiences ($M = 2.57$, $SD = 0.553$) was the only area oftentimes manifested. Meanwhile, mastery experiences ($M = 2.40$, $SD = 0.450$), positive affect ($M = 2.33$, $SD = 0.674$), and social or verbal persuasion ($M = 2.07$, $SD = 0.583$) were rarely manifested, indicating low self-perceived research capability across most domains.

Moreover, presented in Table 2 is the result of the descriptive statistics on the self-perceived classroom-based action research capability in terms of mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, social or verbal persuasion, and positive affect as self-reported by practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga Inc., after the implementation of Project R.I.S.E.

Table 4. Level of Self-Perceived Classroom-Based Action Research Capability Among Practice Teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga Inc., After the Implementation of Project R.I.S.E.ost Estimates for the Project RISE Implementation

Dimensions	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Mastery Experiences	2.89	0.712	Oftentimes Manifested
2. Vicarious Experiences	2.56	0.732	Oftentimes Manifested
3. Social or Verbal Persuasion	3.01	0.709	Oftentimes Manifested
4. Positive Affect	2.85	0.644	Oftentimes Manifested
Total	2.89	0.712	Capable

After the implementation of Project R.I.S.E., the St. Mary's College Baganga Inc., practice teachers' self-perceived capability improved significantly and was described as capable ($M = 2.89$, $SD = 0.712$). All four dimensions were oftentimes manifested, with social or verbal persuasion ($M = 3.01$, $SD = 0.709$) showing the highest increase, followed by mastery experiences ($M = 2.89$, $SD = 0.712$), positive affect ($M = 2.85$, $SD = 0.644$), and vicarious experiences ($M = 2.56$, $SD = 0.732$). This indicates a marked enhancement in their confidence and readiness to engage in classroom-based action research.

Furthermore, presented in Table 3 is the paired sample T-Test result indicating the differential impact on the self-perceived classroom-based action research capability among practice teachers at St. Mary's College Baganga Inc., before and after the implementation of Project R.I.S.E.

A paired samples t-test was conducted to determine the significance of the observed change in self-perceived research capability before and after the seminar-workshop. The results show a highly significant difference with $t(74) = -6.913$, $p < .001$. Hence, H_0 is rejected. This confirms that the improvement in self-perceived capability from pre-intervention ($M = 2.34$) to post-intervention ($M = 2.89$) is not due to chance and can be attributed to the implementation of Project R.I.S.E.

Table 5. Table 3. Level of Self-Perceived Classroom-Based Action Research Capability Among Practice Teachers at St. Mary’s College Baganga Inc., Before the Implementation of Project R.I.S.E.ost Estimates for the Project RISE Implementation

Factor	Measure 1	Measure 2	t	df	p
Self-Perceived Research Capability	Pre	Post	-6.913	74	< .001

Note: * p <0.05, **p <0.01, ***p <0.001

Discussion

Before Project RISE was carried out, practice teachers from St. St. Mary’s College Baganga, Inc., showed only a small level of ability in doing classroom-based action research. There had been no past training or workshops to help them improve in this area. This matches what Hammad and Al-Ani (2021) pointed out—that one big reason teachers struggle with research is the lack of proper training. Vigh (2024) also found that many student teachers find research hard because they don’t get enough support or guidance. These results made it clear that something needed to be done to help future teachers become more confident and capable in doing research.

After the 2-day Project RISE seminar-workshop, there was a clear improvement in how the practice teachers saw their ability to do classroom research. This shows that giving the right kind of training really helps, just like what Murphy et al. (2023) said about the growing importance of research training around the world. Alordiah (2024) also found that training and workshops help boost research performance. Balida et al. (2023) reported the same thing—students got better at writing research papers after attending a workshop. Gault and Allen (2019) added that seminars not only help with research but also with skills like communication and clear thinking. Musa et al. (2021) and Bidwe et al. (2017) both found that workshops helped students write better academic papers. These findings support how effective Project RISE was in helping practice teachers become more skilled in research.

Conclusion

Project R.I.S.E. had a strong and significant positive impact on the self-perceived classroom-based action research capability of the practice teachers. The program effectively increased their confidence and perception of competence across all measured dimensions, validating its design as a relevant and impactful intervention for St. Mary’s College Baganga, Inc., practice teachers' preparation. The result affirmed Bandura’s Social Cognitive Theory, as the intervention leveraged key sources of self-efficacy: mastery experience, modelling, social persuasion, and emotional arousal. These mechanisms empowered practice teachers to see themselves as capable action researchers.

Recommendation

Commission on Higher Education policymakers can include classroom-based action research training as a regular part of teacher education programs. School administrators should support this by scheduling research workshops before practice teaching begins. Faculty members in teacher education should lead simple, step-by-step research seminars focused on real classroom needs. Practice teachers must be encouraged to apply what they learn, starting small, doing classroom research that directly responds to the challenges they face.

Moreover, future researchers should consider using a mixed-method approach to capture both numbers and deeper insights through interviews or reflections. They should also involve more schools to see if the results apply in other settings. Longer interventions—beyond just two days—can give better chances to observe lasting effects. Lastly, using other forms of assessment, like actual research outputs or performance tasks, can give a clearer picture of true research capability. They are encouraged to continue studying issues in education, especially as the Philippine education system faces many ongoing challenges. Research should not stop with one study—there is always something more to learn and improve. By doing more scholarly investigations, researchers can help find better ways to support teachers, students, and schools. Education keeps changing, so research must keep moving forward to keep up and respond to what learners and educators truly need.

Acknowledgement

The researchers would like to sincerely thank the School President and College Dean of St. Mary's College of Baganga, Inc., for her support and guidance. Gratitude is also extended to the teaching and nonteaching staff of the Education Program, the practice teachers who took part in the study, and the research reviewers who shared their insights. The researchers are deeply thankful to their families and friends for their encouragement, and above all, to God, for the strength and wisdom throughout this journey.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest.

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